

MultiLingualGender - WP2

Open Access Report

WP 2 Objectives

1. Map the use and productivity of non-binary or gender-inclusive forms to refer to groups and individuals in different linguistic communities in Latin America and Europe: Spanish, Portuguese, and Italian.
2. Reveal the personal uses and perception of use in other people of different gender inclusive strategies (duplication, neutralization, non-binary innovations) in different areas of the public and private sphere.
3. Verify correlations between perceptions, attitudes of acceptability and attitudes of adoptability of the different gender inclusive forms in the different communities.
4. Systematize potential differences in uses and perceptions around the production modality (written vs. oral), the age of the speakers (under 40 years old vs. over 40 years old), self-perceived gender (cis woman, cis man, non-binary, etc.), and the level of formal schooling (complete high school, undergraduate, postgraduate).
5. Relate the results of the survey to the linguistic policies practiced in each community regarding gender marking.

WP 2 Data analysis

Summary of demographic data for each linguistic community

2.3.1.1. Argentina

Sample size N = 239

Age mean = 39,41 (14,40)

Min=18; Max=85

Gender identity

Cis woman	168	71,49%
Cis man	62	26,38%
Transgender man	2	0,85%
Agendered	1	0,43%
No response	2	0,85%

See complete exploratory analysis here: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18657848>

2.3.1.2. Spain

Sample size N = 178
Age mean = 40,39 (17,62)
Min=18; Max=80

Gender identity

Woman	129	72,42%
Man	44	24,72%
No response	5	2,80%

2.3.1.3. Brazil

Sample size N = 247
Age mean = 39,33 (13,37)
Min= 18 ; Max= 74

Gender identity

Cis woman	114	46,15 %
Cis man	56	22,67 %
Non binary	6	2,43 %
Cisgender	14	5,67 %
Gender fluid	2	0,81 %
Agender	2	0,81 %
Other identities	17	6,88 %
No response	3	1,21 %

2.3.1.4. Italy

Sample size N = 264
Age mean = 41,54 (16,29)
Min= 18 ; Max= 82

Gender identity

Cis woman	164	62.12%
Cis man	95	35.98%
Non binary	2	0.75%
Queer	1	0.37%

Summary of preliminary exploratory data

2.3.2.1. Block A

Argentina

Among the texts of the type "Official documents" most participants perceived a clear bias, with the exception of one fragment in which the generic masculine for feminized tasks instead of the feminine form is used.

Among the "Daily interaction" most participants perceived gender bias in all fragments.

Among the "Pedagogical texts" most of the participants did not perceive bias for gender stereotyping, with the only exception of the fragment in which the use of generic masculine vs non-binary forms is contrasted.

Among the "Journalistic texts" the general scene is less consistent: two of the fragments obtain mostly intermediate answers of the type "It is doubtful, I do not perceive it clearly." However, in all cases the dispersion of responses is much greater than in other types of text, while no response exceeds 35-40%.

Among the texts in the "Advertising" category, there is a very consistent and majority tendency to perceive gender bias, with the sole exception of the text that shows male stereotypes about paternity, in which the response mostly arises "It is doubtful, I do not perceive it clearly." This data will be particularly relevant when making detailed analyses and comparing these results with other communities.

Finally, among the texts of "Social networks", most perceive gender bias, although with different consistency and strength. The text that highlighted female stereotypes in an interaction between women received more dispersed responses.

Spain

There is no consistent perception of bias among "Official documents". In two of the fragments there is a majority perception above 60% while two others exhibit a majority response "No, I do not perceive any bias". That is, extreme responses are the most chosen. In the same sense as in Argentina, the text that uses generic masculine for feminized professions is not perceived as biased.

For "Daily interactions" most of the texts were perceived with a clear gender bias, with one exception where no bias is perceived. This is the fragment showing biases in housework and care tasks. Another point of particular interest for in-depth analysis in all communities.

Among the "Pedagogical texts" in Spain, there were no clear biases either, with one exception, which addresses sexual education issues using the masculine as a generic. In this case, a clear gender bias is perceived, with more than 70% of responses.

For "Journalistic texts" the answers are more scattered in two of the texts and very consistent in another two, in which the bias is clearly perceived. The two less consistent texts are linked to female stereotypes.

This pattern is repeated for texts in the category of "Advertising": two texts are perceived as clearly biased and two others show a great dispersion. Again, these are texts that exhibit particularly feminine stereotypes.

The "Daily Interactions" category showed only one text that generated consistent perception of bias, it was the one that exhibited stereotypes in hetero-cis relationships. However, those who exhibited female stereotypes and related to relationships between women were not perceived as biased.

Brazil

Among official documents submitted for Brazil, there is a clear perception of bias only in two cases; while in the other two texts no gender bias is perceived.

Among everyday interactions, all texts were recognized as gender-biased. However, in one of them the answers have a very dispersed and uneven distribution. This fragment displayed gender stereotypes linked to men and women in child-rearing and childcare tasks. This dimension seems to be even more invisibilized as unbalanced in terms of gender.

Among the journalistic texts, three of the four texts presented were judged as unbiased. Only in one of them gender bias was widely perceived, although the percentage is low and does not reach 38%.

Most strikingly, among the pedagogical texts presented in Brazil, none of them was perceived as gender-biased. In all cases there were biases in the linguistic forms used to refer to men and women and those used as generic forms; however, none was perceived as biased.

Among the texts corresponding to advertising, in three of the four it was perceived a gender bias, although with different consistency. The one referring to men in domestic tasks had more dispersed responses, and the one that related sports activities only to men was not perceived as biased.

Finally, among the social media texts, all were perceived with clear gender bias with very homogeneous responses always exceeding 58%, reaching almost 78% in one case.

It will be especially interesting to analyze qualitatively in detail, which factors drive the perception of bias more strongly and which, instead, are not considered in the judgments.

Italy

Within the community of Italy, in general, more dichotomous patterns are exhibited, not so dispersed within the scale.

For the Official Documents, in two of the cases a gender bias is clearly perceived, while in two others no bias at all is perceived (in three of the four cases, the reports exceed 50%).

Daily exchanges fragments exhibit a clearer pattern towards the detection of gender bias: three of the fragments are classified as gender-biased (usually with more than 55%) and only one is not perceived as biased. This text, in particular, contains biases linked to the male stereotype. In line with what has been found in other communities and previous studies, it will be interesting to investigate whether those texts with male stereotypes are not perceived as biased, but simply neutral; instead, female stereotypes are perceived more clearly as biased.

Between journalistic texts and pedagogical texts there is the greatest degree of dispersion for Italy.

Among the former, there are two texts perceived as clearly biased, with values around 50%, while two others show more dispersed responses. Especially interesting is a text that shows a dispersion almost in quarters (25%) between "yes", "no" and "not very clear." Particularly this text exhibits female profiles in the world of sports.

Among the pedagogical texts, there is a majority in which no bias is perceived, however in one of them there is a contrastive pattern between clear perception (35%) and denial of clear bias (28.5%). This text displays female stereotypes related to upbringing, care and domestic work. It would be particularly interesting to do a comparative analysis with the other communities around these factors.

Finally, in the texts of Social networks and Advertising, gender bias was systematically detected. In most of them, the percentage exceeds 50%, showing a clear strength in the perception of bias. There is, however, an advertising text that shows a more dispersed pattern and a contrast between the extreme positions "yes" (30.8%) and "no" (28.1). It is a fragment that describes male and female roles around domestic and parenting tasks.

2.3.2.2. Block B

Argentina

There are differences in the patterns found due to all factors analysed. In the first place, it should be said that the type of relationship between the partners (their hierarchical or power relationship) is important and conditions both the use report as well as the perception report of the use of different ways to mark gender. The type of communication modality also seems to be a constraint. The written modality seems to facilitate the use of non-binary forms and duplication, while oral communication, in its immediacy, tends to increase both the reported use and the reported perception of generic masculine. The epicene forms or collective nouns appear mostly in written communication in interactions with authorities, showing the highest degree of formality of those forms.

Finally, it is worth highlighting the differences between usage reporting and perception reporting. In both written and oral communication, the generic masculine appears to be more perceived than used, a pattern similar to that of non-binary forms. Whereas

duplication and epicene forms exhibit a more comparable pattern between use and perception reporting, especially in peer-to-peer interaction.

Spain

The generic masculine shows a consistent report of use and perception in Spain. Only two contexts are an exception: written interactions with superiors, in which the use and perception of generic masculine use loses relative strength to duplication and epicene forms. Written peer-to-peer communications follow a similar pattern.

The most salient data in Spain is the very low report of use and perception of use of non-binary forms (with a maximum of 9%); a figure that contrasts clearly with the pattern found in Argentina, where peer interactions show a use and perception report of around 40-50%. This does not allow us to ensure that these are the levels of effective use, but these data do show a high metalinguistic awareness about non-binary forms in Argentina, but not in Spain.

Similarly, duplication, which could have been preferred in Spain at the cost of not using non-binary forms, does not show high levels of usage or perception reporting: only in the context of hierarchical relationship in writing is perceived a use greater than 30%.

Brazil

For block B we have a general pattern with similarities and differences compared to the other communities. Specifically for non-binary forms, as in the case of Argentina and Spain, their use report is low (Argentina is the one that reports the most use), but the report of perception of use by other people increases markedly. That is, people think they perceive its use much more than its use is effectively reported. Those who report it. This consistent data across all communities is particularly interesting to analyze and could be showing the wide diffusion of the discussion especially by detractors of its use that generates the sense of a much more widespread use than actually exists.

Specifically for the personal use report, in written form, majority choices are gender-free forms and duplication in peer interactions. On the other hand, in interactions between people with different hierarchical level or power relationship, duplication and generic masculine is imposed. This shows that, indeed, the type of relationship between interlocutors can ostensibly condition the language forms used.

In the oral form, on the other hand, generic masculine emerges as the majority choice in both types of relationship between interlocutors. However, among peers the second most chosen option are genderless forms, whereas in relationships with hierarchical link, duplication is the second preferred option.

For the use perception report, in addition to the most significant element about perception around non-binary forms, the other noteworthy fact is that the generic male form is reported as the most perceived in all modalities and relationships. Also, duplication is the second most chosen option in all interaction contexts.

Italy

For the community of Italy is also especially marked the pattern that we have already described around non-binary forms in the other communities: their use is reported very

low, however, the perception of use by other people appears strongly increased. That is, the population holds the belief or perception that non-binary forms are more widespread and used than the same community reports using those forms. This pattern is systematic in all contexts and for all types of interaction.

In an initial exploratory analysis, for reporting personal use of inclusive forms in Italy in the written form, a preference for duplication in the first place can be observed (both for peer interaction and within relationships with power hierarchy). Genderless forms also appear second in both cases. When the perception of use by others is reported, generic male is the first option, while duplication is the second.

For the oral form, on the other hand, generic masculine is imposed as the most reported option both for personal use and perception of use by others. In varying proportions this is true of all types of interaction, between peers and among persons with a hierarchical relationship. For all cases, duplication is the second option reported in all cases. It will be interesting to analyze in detail the systematic difference in patterns between written and oral modality.

2.3.2.3. Block C

In this block we specifically discuss the use of non-binary forms in each language and community.

There are closed questions, of type Yes/No/Sometimes, which in turn refer to a series of open-ended questions for justification and argumentation.

To analyze the arguments both in favor of using non-binary inclusive forms and not using them, we propose the following basic taxonomy:

Using

1. Simplicity and comfort
2. Ethical position/respect for people
3. Visibility of diverse identities/promotion of social equality
4. Political/ideological positioning
5. Challenge of dominant positions
6. Inefficiency of the male to include
7. Irony/Sarcasm
8. Others

Not using

1. Imposition of a minority
2. Inefficiency
3. Linguistic purism
4. Difficulty of use
5. Arbitrariness between grammatical gender, sex and social gender
6. Invisibility of the feminine

- 7. Political/ideological motivation
- 8. Absence of massive use

So far, we have concentrated on the arguments against its use in each linguistic community.

Argentina

Use of non-binary forms		
Yes	24	10%
Sometimes	111	46,40%
No	104	43,50%

The most common argument for not using non-binary forms is their difficulty of use, that is to say, the inclusion of a new morpheme in a language with a grammatical gender governing concordance. In these cases, the change in other words is mandatory and seems to be an obstacle that speakers register.

Secondly, there is the argument for linguistic purism, which maintains the position of the linguistic norm as immutable. This argument is repeated in various formats, but the general idea is always that "any variation ruins language".

The third most frequent argument is about a political/ideological position against the inclusive postulates of feminist and sexual diversity movements.

Spain

Use of non-binary forms		
Yes	4	3%
Sometimes	29	16%
No	150	81%

For Spain, the most frequent arguments against the use of non-binary forms coincide with those detected in Argentina. However, as a third argument the notion that non-binary forms are redundant takes hold since the generic masculine is sufficient to refer to all gender identities. This data is in line with the results found for Spain in block B, with a predominant use of generic masculine.

Brazil

Use of non-binary forms		
Yes	13	5,20%
Sometimes	74	29,70%
No	162	65%

In the Brazilian community, the most cited argument against the use of non-binary forms is also linguistic purism and the idea that any variation "ruins" language. It is striking that the second argument used is the absence of mass use, while some participants mention that if people used it more, they would also do so. The two arguments that follow are the difficulty of a new morphological form and (as fourth), a general opposing political-ideological position.

Italy

Use of non-binary forms		
Yes	18	8,49%
Sometimes	41	19,33%
No	125	72,17%